

EUROPEAN

POLICY BRIEF

Citizen Science in the Arts & Humanities

Peter Baeck, Aleks Berditchevskaia, Alexandra Albert, Centre for Collective Intelligence Design, Nesta, London, UK

31 March 2026

INTRODUCTION

Arts-based citizen science can be a powerful tool for engaging citizens not just as data contributors but as co-creators of knowledge and culture. By leveraging arts-based practices such as visual, performative, embodied practices, Arts & Humanities Citizen Science (A&H CS) can help reach groups often marginalised by conventional research and generate new forms of insight rooted in lived experience.

This brief explores what A&H CS is and the potential benefits or added value it brings to citizen science, providing illustrative case studies. As a nascent field within citizen science, there is still some way to go to unlock the full potential of arts-based practices for citizen science within the European research, cultural and innovation policy. Our recommendations are aimed at helping institutions to make use of these approaches more effectively in the years to come.

WHAT IS ARTS & HUMANITIES CITIZEN SCIENCE?

A&H can broadly be defined as *collaborative knowledge production using citizen science with and through art*. It combines methods from the arts and humanities with citizen participation and adheres to the core principles of citizen science while broadening the knowledge base to include:

- **Tacit and embodied knowledge** such as memory, sensory perception, performance is used to enhance data collection on a given topic. For example, community participants might use sound walks, storytelling, or performative re-enactments to capture how local histories are felt, remembered, and experienced in place.

- **Participatory art initiatives** such as photography, theatre, sound mapping, visual design. For example, citizens might co-create photo exhibitions documenting environmental change, produce site-specific theatre exploring local narratives, or generate sound maps capturing the acoustic landscape of their neighbourhood.
- **Co-curation and co-design** such as citizens as active shapers of heritage interpretation and governance. For example, community members might collaboratively design museum exhibits, curate local archives, or participate in decision-making around the preservation of cultural landmarks using citizen science data.

The [COSEA initiative](#) illustrates these different dimensions. The project mobilises coastal communities to collect seaweed specimens and create art-based herbarium specimens that are simultaneously authenticated as cultural artifacts and digitally anchored to their exact geographical collection location. It embraced arts-methods and co-creation of what it calls SeaweedPoetry, where citizens write an 11-word poem based on a specimen and their emotions about the ocean. This helps transform a subjective, sensory experience into formally documented data.

Furthermore, the growing interest in and experimentation with A&H CS is part of a wider movement using arts-based approaches to shift and expand the methodological toolkit for how people are involved in decision making on issues that matter. Methods such as legislative theatre which uses interactive theatre shows where community members act out solutions to situations of oppression, then work with officials to transform them into new laws or changes to existing laws. For example, [Greater Manchester Legislative Theatre](#) in 2020 was used to co-create the city's Homelessness Prevention Strategy 2021-2026.

By embracing diverse methodologies, A&H CS enhances methodological inclusivity and strengthens accountability, aligning directly with EU objectives for socially just and inclusive transitions.

Europe faces urgent challenges of declining trust in democratic institutions, growing social fragmentation, and the demands of a just, green and digital transition. Conventional top-down research frameworks alone cannot deliver the local legitimacy and public trust required to mobilise collective action. Within the broader opportunities in citizen science, A&H CS provides a particular opportunity to restore trust, empower inclusive participation, and integrate diverse cultural and intellectual perspectives into decision making.

Arts & Humanities CS is grounded in the fundamental participatory values and approaches of citizen science, but it also explores how to both apply these approaches in arts and humanities projects or enhance traditional environmental/natural sciences-based CS through arts-based methods that prioritise co-creation, dialogue, and trust. If done well it can lead to several different types of impact, including operational, efficiencies, social inclusion and resilience. These benefits can be understood through three broad models.

Contributory models – efficiency and scale

Contributory A&H CS projects enable cultural and research institutions to unlock large volumes of data quickly and cost-effectively, while engaging wide volunteer networks. They are particularly effective for digitisation, transcription and classification tasks that would otherwise require significant institutional resources.

- [*Birmingham Museums Trust Documentation Detectives*](#) project helped transcribe over 60,000 archival records in one year by 2,700+ volunteers using the Zooniverse platform.
- [*Senses of Stories*](#) is a project run by universities in Canada and Europe to uncover how writers use sensory language to create immersive experiences. It is supported by 1,650+ volunteers using the Zooniverse platform.

Participatory models – inclusion and trust

Participatory approaches build mutual learning and strengthen the relationships between institutions and local communities through involving citizens in the design, analysis and use of research findings. In doing this, they generate richer, more contextual knowledge and can contribute towards fostering long-term trust. Examples of this include:

- [*National Maritime Museum's \(NMM\) Sea People Gallery*](#): This project undertook co-curation with underrepresented communities which led to permanent gallery artworks and institutional reforms embedding co-creation in future exhibitions. As part of the development of four new galleries, the NMM incorporated extensive community consultation and co-curation into the development of its "Sea Things" gallery. One project, Sea People, involved working with underrepresented communities, local schools, colleges, and community groups to create new artworks for the gallery.
- [*Serpentine Gallery's Choral Data Trust*](#): This project engaged 14 choirs across the UK to create a choral dataset which was used to train an AI voice model central to the art exhibition. Alongside contributing to data collection, the choirs were invited to take part in a collective data governance experiment, where they decided the rules for future sharing and re-use of the data.

Transformative models – systemic change

Transformative models engage citizens throughout the full research cycle, enabling them to both identify challenges and opportunities using CS based methods, but also use these insights to develop projects that generate change and impact on their own communities. These projects can help institutions reform and change their practices, empower marginalised groups and generate sustainable solutions to complex societal challenges (see *Case Study: Oeiras Experimenta Living Lab*). An example of a transformative programme is:

- [*PartArt4OW*](#): A European project deploying cascade funding supporting participatory art&science initiatives across Europe that build emotional connection to oceans and mobilise collective action on water sustainability.

Topic: Sustainable Food Systems, Resource Management
Country: Portugal
Communities engaged: More than 2,000 local people from diverse generations and social backgrounds through participatory visits, public events, and collaborative activities.

What they did: This citizen science initiative focused on researching and promoting climate-resilient crops adapted to drought and changing environmental conditions, such as grass pea, sorghum, millets, cereal hybrids, and dryland rice. Implemented through a partnership between ITQB NOVA and the Oeiras Municipality under the Ciência + Cidadã Program, the project brought together scientists, citizens, policymakers, artists, chefs, and local organisations to co-create sustainable and inclusive food systems. Citizen scientists actively participated across research tasks, from sowing and harvesting crops to field maintenance, data collection, protocol improvement, and decision-making, strengthening the social relevance of scientific research. By providing a range of creative and social activities alongside the Living Lab, the project established deeper connections with local residents and gained visibility across a range of forums, ultimately attracting interest from media and decision makers.

Focus on arts and creativity: The Oeiras team undertook a range of creative cooking activities to contextualise the relevance of sustainable food systems to people's daily lives. Researchers and citizen scientists collaborated in the co-creation of sustainable recipes and showcased the ingredients (gathered through the activities of the Living Lab) through culinary workshops at public events.

Systemic benefits – policy durability and transdisciplinarity.

By creating open spaces for dialogue, A&H CS can strengthen the perceived legitimacy of knowledge and improve the durability of policies built on it. It also integrates diverse knowledge forms, tacit, embodied, sensory and scientific, helping policymakers address complex transitions with a more comprehensive evidence base. Arts-based approaches can offer more accessible means to engage the public in complex public and societal challenges. This may be particularly important for working with vulnerable communities or young people (see *Case Study: Nature in our Hands*).

Topic: Biodiversity, Public Trust, Education and Empowerment

Country: United Kingdom

Communities engaged: The project brought together 649 primary school students, 98 staff, 5 local environmental groups/individuals, 2 local creatives /groups, 3 academic researchers as well as local and national policy makers and education professionals.

What they did: The Nature in Our Hands project engaged young learners in environmental stewardship through citizen science. It facilitated students to observe, record, and interpret biodiversity data within their local ecosystems, fostering both scientific literacy and a sense of responsibility for nature. The sessions have not only weaved in elements of the Key Stage 1 and 2 English National Curriculum across Science (Identifying plants and animals, habitats and working scientifically), Geography (Local ecosystems, observation skills and map use), Art and Design (creative expression to represent observations), but cover cross curricular topics such as Citizenship (developing responsibility for the environment) and encouraged critical thinking, collaboration, communication and STEM integration with real-world application. As a result of their creative awareness raising and cohesion building activities within the local community, representatives from the local council are exploring legal arrangements to secure the future of West Rise Marsh under the new East Sussex Unitary Council structure, ensuring long-term protection of this green space.

Focus on arts and creativity: To foster more engaging and deeper connections with the local environment for the young people involved, the project involved students in producing different creative outputs including posters, papier mache sculptures and drawings. Overall, 1214 creative pieces were produced by students during the project.

The intersection of arts, culture, and citizen science is a nascent field with significant potential, but its systematic adoption is hampered by institutional inertia, lack of collaboration and experimentation and policy criteria developed primarily for quantifiable hard scientific research. To accelerate the integration of A&H CS into the European Research Area (ERA), policy must focus on creating the structural conditions necessary for greater experimentation and validation of non-traditional knowledge outputs.

1. Judging value beyond traditional science metrics

A significant barrier to integrating Arts & Humanities Citizen Science is the conflict between the evidence generated and the way traditional science is often judged by funding bodies. Reproducibility and quantifiable data are standards which are, in many cases, ill-suited for creative projects that rely on cultural or social outputs.

Because artistic and performative projects are often open-ended or capture embodied knowledge (such as emotion, sensory input, or lived experience), they are at risk of being excluded when evaluation criteria demand primarily numerical data forms or hard evidence. This creates a validation/assessment challenge, where the social, democratic, and trust-building value generated by A&H CS cannot be officially captured or legitimised by policy. Likewise artists and creative practitioners could benefit from the more systematised methods of measuring and reporting impact that have been developed within the citizen science community.

To overcome this, there should be wider recognition of more comprehensive assessment frameworks that also emphasise social impact. This requires funding bodies to attribute value to alternative success metrics, for example: participatory validity (the extent of stakeholder involvement), empathic validity (the degree to which mutual understanding and trust increased), and most critically, catalytic validity (how useful the research was in presenting new possibilities for social action). By adopting these broader evaluation methods and funding tools to document social impact, policy can ensure that research quality, such as that done by A&H CS initiatives, is judged by its ability to foster real-world social and policy change, rather than scientific publication counts alone

2. Strategic support for experimentation and collaboration

As a new field, A&H CS requires focused policy mechanisms to foster interdisciplinary collaboration and overcome fragmented resources and expertise.

- **Mandate collaborative formats:** funding instruments should explicitly mandate and resource the integration of the S+T+ARTS approach, in relevant funding calls and other EU initiatives. This could ensure that artistic and cultural methodologies are viewed as essential R&I drivers, not just outreach.
- **Leverage Creative Europe:** utilise Creative Europe's Cooperation Projects (which offer high co-funding rates and support transnational collaboration) and mobility schemes (like Culture Moves Europe) to fund the community building, knowledge transfer, and rapid co-creation phases of A&H CS projects. This provides the flexible financial support necessary for experimentation and cross-border learning.
- **Incentivise and increase visibility of interdisciplinarity:** promote interdisciplinary co-creation through prizes and events like Ars Electronica. This can accelerate the transfer of expertise between artists, researchers, and citizens, as well as encouraging wider uptake of these approaches due to associated prestige.

Systemic integration requires a coordinated effort, targeting financial structures, institutional culture, and practitioners.

EU/National Funders

- **Promote Arts&Humanities Citizen Science through existing funding schemes:** Embed A&H CS explicitly within instruments like the New European Bauhaus and Horizon Europe Cluster 2, which already fund projects connecting inclusion, design, and local democracy.
- **Clarify IPR and open licensing requirements:** Require that Creative Commons licensing (CC-BY) be a mandatory condition for all publicly funded A&C-CS data and co-created outputs. This could help ensure public reuse and the long-term legacy of institutional cultural data assets.
- **Fund methodological capacity:** Dedicate funding streams (e.g., through Coordination and Support Actions and cascade funding opportunities) to develop standardised training and tools that improve methodological awareness and establish communities of practice.

Cultural Institutions and Public Bodies

- **Shift to co-creative models:** Incentivise and resource the institutional transformation from viewing citizens merely as data transcribers (contributory models) to co-creators of cultural and research knowledge.
- **Streamline compensation:** Reform internal financial and procurement protocols to reduce the bureaucratic friction involved in compensating citizen participants (e.g., payment, travel reimbursement). This is vital to uphold Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) principles and ensure participation is accessible to marginalized or low-income groups.
- **Leverage CS to build trust:** Position citizen science as a core component of institutional strategies aimed at strengthening accountability, transparency, and trustworthiness with local communities to reinforce democratic principles.

Practitioners and Researchers

- **Raise methodological awareness:** Actively adopt and promote the principles of participatory research, focusing on providing clear, concise project descriptions that emphasise volunteer benefits and actionable outcomes to increase recruitment and retention.
- **Document non-traditional outputs:** Systematically document and disseminate outputs generated through embodied and tacit knowledge processes, explicitly articulating how they meet catalytic and ethical validity criteria, thereby setting new standards for policy evaluation.

PROJECT INFORMATION

PROJECT NAME

IMPETUS

AUTHORS

Peter Baeck, Aleks Berditchevskaia, Alexandra Albert,
Centre for Collective Intelligence Design, Nesta, London,
UK

CONSORTIUM

Ars Electronica, Linz, Austria
European Science Engagement Association, Vienna,
Austria King's College London, London, United Kingdom
Nesta, London, United Kingdom
Science for Change, Hospitalet De Llobregat, Spain
T6 Ecosystems srl, Roma, Italy
Zabala Innovation Consulting, S.A., Navarra, Spain

FUNDING SCHEME

IMPETUS is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101058677. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

DURATION

July 2022 – June 2026 (48 Months)

BUDGET

5,000,000 Euros, Contributed by the European Commission and UK Research and Innovation

WEBSITE

<https://impetus4cs.eu/>

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We are grateful to our CSIs for sharing their stories and our partners at T6 Ecosystems for reviewing this policy brief.

CITATION

European Policy Brief: Citizen Science in the Arts & Humanities. Baeck, P., Berditchevskaia, A. and Albert, A. (2026)